

The Focus of Teaching Innovation in Comparative Ideological and Political Education Classes in the New Era

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ABSTRACT: As an important subject branch of ideological and political education, comparative ideological and political education is an important support for the postgraduate training of ideological and political education majors. The teaching of comparative ideological and political education in the new era has many new features in terms of teaching subjects, teaching objects, teaching methods and teaching environment, etc. These features bring new dilemmas to the teaching of comparative ideological and political education in the new era, and in the face of these dilemmas it is necessary to carry out teaching innovations around teaching contents, teaching management and assessment methods to provide reference for promoting curriculum construction and reform.

KEYWORDS: New era; comparative ideological and political education; teaching innovation

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Comparative ideological and political education is a product of the mutual appreciation of civilisations in the era of globalisation. It takes the various forms of ideological and political education as its research object, and through the comparative analysis and universal refinement of the various forms of ideological and political education, it achieves mutual knowledge, understanding and reference among the various forms of ideological and political education, and thus grasps the universal way of ideological and political education, which fundamentally provides effective solutions to the problems that exist in the evolution of human civilisation. This will provide a plurality of wisdom for effectively solving the problems of ideology in the evolution of human civilisation. In this new era, we will examine the new features and circumstances of teaching comparative ideological and political education courses, and thus promote the deepening development of teaching innovation in comparative ideological and political education courses.

I. NEW FEATURES OF TEACHING COMPARATIVE IDEOLOGICAL AND POLITICAL EDUCATION CLASSES IN THE NEW ERA

As a sub-discipline of ideological and political education, comparative ideological and political education is a science that uses comparative methods to gain knowledge through a frame of reference and conducts intercultural and interdisciplinary research in the field of ideological and political education in order to promote the development of the theory and practice of ideological and political education in the country (region)[1]. Faced with the unprecedented changes of the past century, the teaching of comparative ideological and political education courses has taken on new characteristics in terms of teaching environment, teaching methods, teaching subjects and teaching techniques.

1.1 The globalisation of the teaching environment of comparative ideological education courses

If we say that the teaching environment of comparative ideological and political education courses in the past was mainly the "local knowledge" of human beings in closed civilizational circles, then, in the open world picture of "history becoming world history", the teaching environment of comparative ideological and political education courses must This has become a realistic context for the innovation of teaching comparative ideological and political education courses, and has also shaped the open character of the knowledge system of comparative ideological and political education[2]. In recent years, international exchange and cooperation in higher education and cross-border education have been enriched and brought closer together, with more and more global campuses, joint programmes, and mixed mobility projects involving multiple countries.

1.2 The extensive use of comparative teaching methods in the teaching practice of the curriculum

Comparison is an important way of thinking and research method. Comparative research can expand the dual dimension of time and space in people's understanding and enable them to grasp more accurately the objective laws of human social development. It is only through such comprehensive and in-depth "research and comparison" that it is possible to analyse in depth the various forms of development of the object of study and the internal links between them. It is only after this fundamental work has been completed that "the movement of reality can be properly described". It is only through an in-depth analysis of the specific forms of ideological and political education practices in different historical time and space that it is possible to deeply grasp the general laws of the evolution and development of various forms of ideological and political education, to provide a theoretical base for the innovative development of comparative ideological and political education teaching, and to explore the realistic way forward[3]. Comparative teaching research provides a scientific tool for analysing the ideologies and education of different historical eras and societies. The value of comparative ideological and political education teaching lies not only in finding similarities and differences, but also in seeing through the phenomena to the essential laws behind them, and in understanding, learning from and reflecting on the practice of ideological and political education in countries around the world. "It is a way of thinking that should be integrated into the whole process of teaching comparative ideological and political education. "It is not only a methodological tool, but also a way of thinking that gives an important value to comparative ideological and political education teaching.

1.3 Diversity of teachers is an important feature of university teachers in the new era.

Without the experience of studying and living abroad, teachers cannot comprehensively and deeply understand the culture and customs of foreign countries, and cannot concretely explain the theories and practices of foreign related disciplines. This is why the teaching of comparative courses requires teachers to have a foreign cultural background and study experience so that they can better assimilate the content, teaching methods and educational philosophy of foreign disciplines. The history of higher education shows that the more international the teaching staff and the more diverse their backgrounds, the more students will be attracted and the deeper the mutual understanding between teachers and students will be, which will be more conducive to the improvement of the quality of course teaching.

1.4 The advent of the era of big data technology.

With the continuous development of information technology, such as network technology and mobile internet technology, and the popularity of mobile communication and social networks, the amount of global data and information has exploded. Big Data is not only a technology, but also "a value and methodology". In the era of Big Data, people's thoughts, activities and social relationships can be recorded in the form of data. Human behaviour is no longer regarded as an independent event that happens by chance, but through the collection, collation and analysis of a large amount of data, the interdependent and interconnected internal relationship between various behaviours can be found, so that the judgement of individual behaviour patterns, life habits and the prediction of upcoming events can be achieved. This deep communication logic has changed dramatically from traditional communication methods, not only improving communication efficiency, but also reducing communication costs.

II. The dilemma facing the teaching of comparative ideological and political education classes in the new era

With the deepening of the teaching practice of postgraduate comparative ideological and political education courses, the curriculum, course content, teaching methods and means, teaching conditions and teaching effects of comparative ideological and political education under traditional education have been difficult to meet the needs of postgraduate education. The course study has not played its proper role in cultivating the comprehensive ability of academic postgraduates, especially the cultivation of innovative ability.

2.1 The teaching content of comparative ideological and political education courses is outdated and not very cutting-edge, and the quality of the teaching content needs to be improved.

The teaching content is a fundamental part of the teaching of comparative ideological and political education courses, and it focuses on solving the problem of "what to teach". In the process of teaching the course, I collected as many domestic and foreign comparative ideological and political education textbooks as possible, but after careful review, I found that the textbooks really suitable for postgraduate classroom teaching are really rare, and their inapplicability is mainly reflected in: First, the knowledge is too old, such textbooks are often titled comparative comparative ideological and political education textbooks or works, basically to static introduction of the world's ideological and political education The content is relatively old and still limited to the introduction of comparative ideological and political education in universities between different countries, with a high degree of overlap in the content of some textbooks. The second is that the content is rather esoteric and extensive, which makes it unsuitable for postgraduate teaching. This type of textbook mainly introduces theories of ideological and political education, including the recently published Zhou Qi's Comparative Ideological and Political Pedagogy of East China University of Political Science and Law, which systematically introduces Marxist ideological and political education theories, ancient Chinese ideological and political education theories and modern ideological and political education theories of Western countries, and Kang Xiuyun's Research on the Frontiers of Comparative Ideological and Political Pedagogy of Northeast Normal University, which directly addresses the issues that must be answered in the construction of the discipline of comparative ideological and political education. The study of the basic theoretical questions of the discipline that must be answered for the construction of the discipline of pedagogy, exploring the basic concepts, nature of the discipline, research objectives and research paradigms of the discipline. This kind of work provides a systematic introduction to the main theories in comparative ideological and political education, but the content is rather esoteric and not suitable for teaching in postgraduate courses.

2.2 The teaching process emphasizes the transmission of knowledge but not the cultivation of ability.

In the postgraduate education stage, students' independent learning has become an important way of learning, and the method of "research-based teaching" should be adopted as far as possible in postgraduate

teaching to consciously strengthen the cultivation of postgraduates' independent learning ability, focusing on cultivating and exercising postgraduates' thinking ability, scientific research ability and innovation ability. From the current course research situation, classroom teaching is still mainly based on teachers' lectures, lacking in-depth analysis of ideological and political education theory and practice. Most of the postgraduates think that the current course has not fully played its role in cultivating students' thinking ability, academic training and innovation ability, and most of them rate the course as "unsatisfactory" or "average".

2.3 The capacity of teaching faculty needs to be improved.

The teaching of comparative ideological and political education courses requires the creation of a team of teachers with an open international perspective, good international exchange skills and solid professional theoretical qualities. Due to the influence of factors such as the disciplinary background, knowledge structure and research interests of the education subject, there is still more room for deeper development in terms of diversity and refinement of methods. First, language skills need to be improved. Advocates of linguistic relativism argue that different languages are different ways of thinking, different worldviews, different metaphysics, and that they are not commensurable with each other. Secondly, information retrieval skills. With the rapid development of global information technology and the influx of massive amounts of data, accessing and transmitting valuable information in an easy and quick way is conducive to improving the quality of teaching and learning. However, the poor information retrieval skills of some teachers seriously affect the normal operation of quality teaching and learning.

2.4 The management of the teaching process and conditions of the course are relatively weak.

Although the university and the college have established a postgraduate course management system and taken corresponding measures in curriculum setting and audit, teacher qualification recognition, teaching process management, teaching quality monitoring and evaluation, course assessment and grade evaluation, teaching reform and course construction. However, at the same time, it is also found that the review of postgraduate courses by the training units is not standardized enough, and some of them are just formal, with unclear authority and responsibility for course setting, duplication of courses, ambiguous levels and the phenomenon of "setting courses according to teachers". In terms of course supervision and evaluation, the training units have formulated their own teaching quality monitoring index systems through lecture listening, inspection, supervision, interview, discussion, questionnaire survey, student evaluation and expert evaluation. However, in general, the management of postgraduate courses emphasizes objectives rather than processes, and system design rather than supervision and accountability, etc. is more common.

2.5 There is a need for innovation in the way teaching is assessed.

When there is teaching, there is examination, and examination is an indispensable part of the teaching organization of colleges and universities. Under the original teaching mode, the assessment of comparative ideological and political education courses is mainly the submission of course papers. This assessment method used to play a great role in checking students' knowledge mastery and urging them to study. With the changes in the current teaching environment, the problems of this assessment method have gradually emerged: the content of the examination is single and there is a lack of comprehensive evaluation of students' abilities. Course papers can test students' understanding and mastery of course knowledge, but not their ability to express themselves orally, organise and coordinate, or collect information.

III. The focus of teaching innovation in comparative ideological and political education in the new era

The Opinions of the Ministry of Education on Comprehensively Deepening Curriculum Reform and Implementing the Fundamental Task of Educating People for Virtue clearly states that "we should follow the latest developments in curriculum reform abroad and learn from international experience". On the basis of a comprehensive understanding of the construction of comparative ideological and political education courses for

postgraduates at home and abroad and the successful experiences of developed countries, the group proposes the following recommendations for the innovation of comparative ideological and political education courses for postgraduates in China.

3.1 The teaching methods are structured.

Promoting the structuring of teaching methods is based on the overall vision, reflecting on the existing methods of comparative ideological and political education, grasping the inner logical connection among them, promoting the coupling between them, and presenting them in a complete and unified thinking logic and theoretical form. One is the practical pedagogy. As comparative ideological and political pedagogy focuses primarily on methodological training, without hands-on, personal practice, the situation is likely to arise: i.e. I understand what I hear, but I don't know how to use it. To avoid this, it is necessary to supplement it with appropriate post-class assignments. During the teaching process, students' comparative thinking and comparative skills are enhanced by arranging for them to do a debriefing of their course work.

3.2 Expand the content of teaching and learning.

The teaching content must be carefully selected, deeply excavated and refined and sublimated. The teaching of comparative ideological and political education courses is not only based on a kind of examination of itself, but also to be able to answer the hot issues in comparative ideological and political education research in the new era, to better respond to the development of comparative ideological and political education, to deepen and expand the theoretical domain of comparative ideological and political pedagogy, comparative ideological and political education teaching should have both an empirical analysis of the practice of extra-territorial ideological and political education, a Theoretical analysis and institutional analysis of extra-territorial ideological and political education are also necessary. The teaching of comparative ideological and political education courses needs to further deepen the thematic research of specific theoretical domains in the future, such as the comparative study of ecological values education; it needs to open up the theoretical domain of comparative ideological and political education in different contexts, such as the comparative study of ideological and political education under the new crown pneumonia epidemic.

3.3 Enhance the international perspective of course teachers.

Strengthening the international perspective of teachers in comparative ideological and political education programmes is a systematic, comprehensive, complex and important project. It requires the concerted and concerted efforts of multiple forces and multiple levels. The teaching of comparative ideological and political education courses covers a wide range of disciplines such as culture, political science, sociology, history, art and religion. The key to improving the quality of classroom teaching is to have certain international exchange channels, language communication skills, cross-cultural research skills and an in-depth grasp of the subject theory of comparative ideological and political education. On a macro level, the cultivation and enhancement of the international perspective of university teachers mainly depends on the design and supply of relevant policies at the national level. Therefore, the national level should formulate corresponding international teacher cultivation standards and cultivation system in response to the requirements of globalization development on the internationalization level of talents, and introduce corresponding policy support system, so as to regulate and guide the direction of international vision of university teachers from the national level. Secondly, we should focus on reshaping the conditions and environment of comparative ideological and political education courses with an international perspective. In the middle level, the cultivation and enhancement of the international vision of teachers of comparative ideological and political education courses mainly depends on the conditions, environment and specific policy guidance provided by the school where the comparative ideological and political education courses are held for the cultivation of teachers' international vision. In the new era, teachers in universities should actively adapt to the development of internationalisation and informatisation of higher education, follow the requirements of the standard system for the international development of talents and talent training system formulated at the national level, as well as the system and policy system of postgraduate courses,

actively formulate practical measures for the international development of talents in our university, from the system to human, material and financial resources, and focus on the needs of cultivating talents with an international perspective in comparative ideology and political education courses. The university is also committed to providing a high-quality match between the international perspective of education courses and the needs of cultivating talents, and providing good software and hardware. Thirdly, we are committed to reshaping the teaching staff of comparative ideological and political education courses with an international perspective. From a microscopic point of view, the key to cultivating the international perspective of teachers in comparative ideological and political education courses lies in the international parenting ability of comparative ideological and political education teachers, and the key to cultivating the international perspective of students in comparative ideological and political education courses lies in the deconstruction and reconstruction of comparative ideological and political education course teachers from an international perspective. Teachers of comparative ideological and political education courses should reconstruct their own educational knowledge system, competence system and cultural system through various channels and ways, in order to lay a solid foundation for the cultivation and enhancement of international perspectives in comparative ideological and political education courses; actively promote the reform and innovation of teaching perspectives, lead the teaching perspectives with international perspectives, construct an international perspective in the theoretical framework of problem analysis and interpretation, and enhance the international perspective of comparative ideological and political education courses. In the reconstruction of the international perspective of the discourse system of teaching contents, aiming at the cultivation of international talents and the actual situation of students, the reconstruction of arguments, discourses and argument materials in teaching should be selected on a global scale, and the international and global nature of the content of teaching discourse should be continuously expanded, so as to continuously enhance the international perspective of comparative ideology and political education courses. The International Perspective of Political Education Courses.

3.4 Improve the quality assurance system and standardise the process management.

Establish a special organization and management agency responsible for curriculum setting, coordination and management. Firstly, it organizes the demonstration of the competence cultivation program of ideological and political education majors, is responsible for coordinating teachers to offer relevant cultivation courses, strengthens the conditions of access to postgraduate courses, and implements regular and process supervision of the courses offered, regularly checks the implementation of postgraduate course teaching to ensure the systemic, hierarchical and sustainable nature of postgraduate courses. The focus is on establishing a set of scientific, reasonable and operable evaluation index system and reward and punishment system for postgraduate courses or classroom teaching, providing timely feedback on evaluation information, urging and helping teachers in charge of the courses to analyze the evaluation results, adjust teaching strategies in a targeted manner, perfect and improve course teaching, and effectively improve teaching quality. The transmission carriers of the knowledge system of the subject of comparative ideological and political education are specifically manifested in textbooks, periodicals and course lectures, which carry the specific form of the subject knowledge system and undertake the historical task of spreading the subject knowledge, so we should pay attention to the effective construction of the transmission carriers of its knowledge form. In terms of teaching materials and publications, national textbooks are used in the teaching process, and in terms of journal articles, students are introduced to the important journals in the field. In terms of course construction, based on the realistic demands of student access, research-based participatory teaching is actively adopted to enhance interest in learning, online teaching tools are used to enhance the enjoyment of learning, teaching links inside and outside the classroom are implemented to broaden theoretical perspectives, challenging assignments are assigned to enhance subject awareness, and efforts are made to build the Comparative Ideological and Political Education course into an excellent course that students genuinely enjoy, benefit from and remember throughout their lives.

3.5 Improve the assessment methods of comparative ideological and political education courses.

Course assessment is an important part of the teaching of postgraduate comparative ideological and political education courses, and it is also the baton of how postgraduates learn comparative ideological and political education courses. Scientific and reasonable course assessment can mobilize the enthusiasm and initiative of postgraduates to learn comparative ideological and political education courses, while unreasonable assessment methods can inhibit or hinder postgraduates' learning of comparative ideological and political education courses. The assessment and evaluation mechanism of traditional postgraduate comparative ideological and political education course teaching is not sound enough, the assessment form is single and there is a large subjective arbitrariness. The innovative course assessment of postgraduate comparative ideological and political education course should achieve three equal importance: teacher assessment and student assessment, process assessment and result assessment, theoretical assessment and practical assessment, and realize the diversification of assessment subjects, standardization of assessment procedures and scientific assessment methods[4]. Its innovation is mainly manifested in two aspects: First, the teacher-student assessment is given equal importance. Traditionally, the assessment of postgraduate comparative ideological and political education courses is teacher-oriented, with a single assessment subject, and students are completely passive objects to be assessed and treated as management objects, and their learning initiative and enthusiasm are greatly restricted. The inquiry-based teaching introduces the student assessor mechanism, realising that teachers and students are the same assessment subject, with each teacher and student assessor having one vote and the same weighting of assessment scores, making up for the long absence of students as the assessment subject. As student assessors also have to carry out mutual assessment in a certain way, they should be guided to standardise, honest, objective and fair assessment, so as to avoid assessment being a formality. Secondly, the process assessment and result assessment are both important. The traditional postgraduate comparative ideological and political education course assessment is the final examination, which is a course paper-based result assessment method. The result assessment cannot fully reflect the degree of effort in the learning process of postgraduates, but on the contrary, it will cause an unobjective evaluation of students who usually study hard, actively participate in classroom discussions and have a high attendance rate, and may even discourage some postgraduates' initiative and enthusiasm in learning. In contrast, inquiry-based teaching focuses on both result assessment and learning process assessment. As members of the inquiry group, how much they contribute, whether they participate in the discussion of questions, debate of ideas and answer questions in class in the results reporting session are all important aspects of the process assessment. The process assessment runs through the whole process of inquiry-based teaching and reflects the postgraduate students' attitude, ability and effectiveness in learning the course more comprehensively and objectively, changing the original misconception that you can pass or even get better grades by just blitzing before the examination.

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